

A novel frameshift mutation of the PSENN gene discovered in a Chinese family with Dowling-Degos disease And Literature Review

Running head: A mutation of the PSENN gene discovered in DDD

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Abstract:

Background: Dowling-Degos disease(DDD MIM: 615327) is a rare autosomal dominant genodermatosis characterized by progressively reticular hyperpigmentation mainly affecting flexures. such as the neck, axilla, chelidon and areas below the breasts and groin, and has obvious heterogeneity. In the past, *KRT5* (OMIM 179850) , *POFUT1* (OMIM 615327) and *POGLUT1* (OMIM 615696) have been identified to be the pathogenic gene of DDD.

Literature Review: In several researches, DDD (Dowling Degos Disease) has been linked with different genes. For example Horner et al. claim that one of many keratin 5 gene's loss-of-function mutation is what causes DDD. Hanneken et al. also described that in most DDD patients and a small number of GGD (Gali Gali Disease) patients, mutations in the keratin 5 gene (*KRT5*) have been linked. Ahmed et al. claim that mutations in the *POGLUT1* gene result in a disseminated, papular clinical appearance, mutations in the keratin 5 (*KRT5*) gene promote a reticular distribution pattern. According to Mancy and Abdullah (2022), DDD is caused by several gene mutations like *POGLUT1*, *POFUT1* and *PSENN* genes, as well as keratin 5 (*KRT5*). According to Papadopoulou et al., the clinical manifestation is caused by mutations in many genes. While *POGLUT1* gene mutations result in a widespread, papular clinical manifestation, keratin 5 (*KRT5*) gene mutations prefer a reticular distribution pattern. According to Garcovich et al., Dowling Degos Disease (DDD; MIM 179850, 615327, and 615696) has also been associated with a deficient NOTCH signalling. The NOTCH signalling system, which is crucial for maintaining the stability of the hair follicle tissue and other skin appendages, is improved by the *POFUT1*, *POGLUT1*, and *PSENN* gene therapies. Peter et al. stated that *POGLUT1* is a crucial modulator of Notch signalling because it binds O-linked glucose to serine residues in Notch receptors that resemble repetitions of the epidermal growth factor. It also regulates the development, maturation, and segmentation of keratinocytes and melanocytes and is crucial for maintaining the homeostasis of cutaneous cells. These and other findings indicate that mutations in *POGLUT1* that result in abnormalities in Notch signalling will contribute to aberrant pigmentation and keratinocyte shape (Peter et al., 2020). Loss of Notch1 and Notch2 in mice leads to abnormal pigmentation (Wilson et al., 2017). Horner et al., (2011) also suggested that Patients with Galli-Galli Disease exhibit similar mutations, and the condition is now regarded as a subgroup of DDD.

Dowling-Degos Disease can manifest either sporadic or autosomal dominant pattern. Several case series and individual case reports cited by Horner et al. (2011) claim that women are more likely than males to experience it. We think more information need to be revealed about Dowling Degos Disease to make it an independent and specific disease pattern as this disease has close relationship with other similar types of diseases. For instance Ahmed et al. claim that DDD can imitate ADMH (Acquired dermal macular hyperpigmentation). Presenilin Enhancer Protein 2 (*PEN-2*) is a subunit of the -secretase enzyme complex and is encoded by *PSENN* (Peter et al., 2021). The other components of this complex include anterior pharynx deficient, presenilin, and nicastrin (Peter et al., 2021). The Notch receptors that are required for the activation of Notch signalling are cleaved intracellularly by the gamma-secretase enzyme complex (Peter et al., 2021). It has been documented that Indian individuals with HS (Hydradenitis Suppurativa) and DDD also had the *PSENN* gene mutation (Peter et al., 2021). According to Garcovich et al., (2020), patients with mutations in *PSENN* who have both pathologies

seem to confirm a potential link between two seemingly unrelated conditions. However we have found and shown in this paper a novel frameshift mutation in *PSENE* gene for DDD in a Chinese family by doing whole exome sequencing. As this finding has not yet been done in relevant researches and literatures we think it can lead to further understanding of DDD in a broader spectrum.

Methods: In this study, we performed the whole-exome sequencing analyses of a large Chinese DDD family, the results were compared against 100 healthy control patients.

Results: No mutations in the *KRT5*, *POFUT1*, or *POGLUT1* genes were found. However, whole-exome sequencing revealed a novel frameshift mutation, c.168_169delTG, in the *PSENE* (OMIM 613737) in seven DDD-afflicted patients. This mutation was not present in healthy individuals of the affected family, nor was it found in any of the healthy controls outside of this family.

Conclusions: Our findings suggest that this novel frameshift mutation, c.168_169delTG, in *PSENE* can be responsible for causing DDD in this family, and further enhances our understanding of the clinical features and genetic pathogenesis of DDD.

Keywords: Genodermatosis, Dowling-Degos disease (DDD), Whole-exome sequencin, *PSENE*, Gene mutation.

Introduction

Dowling-Degos disease (DDD) is a rare autosomal dominant hyperpigmentary disorder. Patients usually present with reticulate pigmented and with small, dark-brown hyperkeratotic papules anomaly mainly affecting flexures and great skin folds, that usually appears and/or worsens after puberty^[1-4]. It was first described by Dowling and Freudenthal in 1938, and confirmed to be a distinct clinical entity by Degos and Ossipowk in 1954, then designated as Dowling-Degos Disease (DDD) by Wilson-Jones and Grice in 1978^[5-7]. A variety of mutations in the *KRT5*, *POFUT1*, *POGLUT1* genes have been identified in DDD individuals^[8,9,10]. Recently, *PSENE* mutations were identified in familial affected by acne inversa(AI) and comanifestation of DDD^[11,12].

Here, we investigated a multiplex DDD family which are absent from *KRT5*, *FOUTI*, *POGLUT1* mutations by exome sequencing analyses. A novel c.168_169delTG, in *PSENE* was confirmed to be a causal gene. This result was identified by Sanger, which sequencing to be present in affected family members, absent in unaffected individuals.

We thought the novel mutation in the *PSENE* may be in connection with clinical presentations, which differ from those previously described^[10-13-14].

Materials and Methods

Subjects and Clinical Presentation

Our study was approved by the ethics committee. We recruited a large Chinese DDD family, which included totaling 11 affected and 53 unaffected (Figures 1). Otherwise 100 unrelated healthy

controls were also Sanger sequenced. The proband was a 44-year-old woman who first noticed hyperpigmentation on her abdomen, perineum, groin, axillae and thighs at age 18. The hyperpigmentation progressively increased, and gradually spread over other parts of her body. Physical examination showed dark brown macules on her axillae, groin, perineum and crissum. In addition, there were some pitted scars on the perioral area and comedones on the nose, face, neck and chest (Figures 2ABC). Skin biopsies were performed from the comedonal lesions on her neck and pigmented lesions on her right ankle respectively. A dilated hair follicle with follicular plugging was observed in comedonal lesions. Hyperpigmented lesions showed hyperkeratosis, irregular elongated thin branching rete ridges growing down into the dermis with increased basal melanin pigmentation (Figures 3AB). Electron microscopy revealed a large number of melanosomes in the melanocytes with zonal distribution (Figures 3CD). The diagnosis of Dowling-Degos disease was definitely established on the basis of distinct clinical manifestations, histopathological and electron microscopic findings^[15].

Her father, a 78-year-old man, had hyperpigmented macules and comedones on his nose at the age of 48 years old. These macules gradually increased in number and involved his whole body, particularly in the flexures of his waist, abdomen, axillae, groin and scrotum, buttock and lower limb (Figures 2DEFG). He had a history of surgical resection of squamous cell carcinoma in the left upper eyelid. Skin examination showed a large number of reticulate dark brown macules over his waist, abdomen, back, axillae, groin and scrotum, buttock and lower limb. Some comedones and pitted scars were observed on his perioral area.

Fig1. The pedigree of the family with DDD. The arrow denotes the proband.

Fig 2. Clinical Photographs of Individuals with DDD

Skin lesions of proband (III6) (A, B and C). Comedones on her nose, depressed scars on her perioral. Brown or black macules on her vulva area and perioral.

Skin lesions of the proband's father (II3)(D,E,F and G). Brown macules, comedones and pitted scars in his armpits, back and groin.

Fig 3. Histological and Electron Microscopy of Skin from Proband with DDD

(A and B)The histological findings from skin lesions with DDD. (A) The histological findings of hyperpigmented macules showed downward elongation of rete ridges with remarkable melanins in the basal layer. (B)The histological findings of comedonal lesions showed a dilated hair follicle with follicular plugging. (A:HE stain, $\times 400$,B: HE stain, $\times 400$). (C and D)Electron Microscopy of Skin from DDD and control. (C) A large number of melanosomes in the melanocytes with zonal distribution in hyperpigmented macules of DDD patients. (D) A little melanosome in the control skin.

Whole-exome sequencing analysis

For whole-exome sequencing, two patients (The proband and her father) were selected for whole-exome sequencing using the Illumina hiseq X-TEN high-throughput sequencer by Beijing

Huada Gene Technology Co, Ltd. Firstly the data of two patients (II3, III6) were compared with 1000G (1000 Genomes Project),ESP(NHLBI Exome Sequencing Project), PVFD (BGI internal database, the Asian group), Hap map (Haplotype Map), ExAc(Exome Aggregation Consortium), CG, Welllderly as well as three internal database BGI total of 10 normal population database, removed the Indel and SNP appearing in each database, got the first-level database. Then secondly took the intersection of the first-level database, which is the unique mutations of the two patients, got the second-level database. And then filtered mutations affect "LOW" and "MEDIUM" mutation in the secondary database. We got three-level database. After having filtered out suspicious mutations we used Mutation Taster software to predict the impact

of an observed mutation. This allowed us to determine which mutations were most likely to play a role in DDD in this large afflicted family. We identified the gene *PSENEN* as a primary candidate. To verify the role of this *PSENEN* mutation, primers were designed to amplify the candidate gene *PSENEN* (F1 5'-TTGGGTGTGGGAGAGTTTCTT-3', F2 5'-TGCTCTCCACTTCCCTAGA -3'), and PCR products were directly sequenced by sanger sequencing in 14 additional members of this family (7 patients and 7 unaffected individuals) along with 100 unrelated healthy controls.

Results

Whole-exome sequencing

We sequenced the entire exome in two patients (III:6 and II:3) from this family. On average, each sample had a total of 168,213,194 effective reads and 99.33% of the 60.46 Mb target regions were covered at 10 X or more. A total of 159,506 SNP including 2,415 new SNP were identified in DDD individuals. The identified heterozygous variants were filtered through the 98.48% dbSNP and 92.94% Genomes Project. These remaining variants included 13,165 synonymous mutations and 12,608 missense mutations.

Firstly the data were filtered from 10 databases (1000G (1000 Genomes Project), ESP(NHLBI Exome Sequencing Project), PVFD (BGI internal database, the Asian group), Hap map(Haplotype Map), ExAc(Exome Aggregation Consortium) ,

CG , Wellredly as well as three internal database BGI total of 10 normal population database) , and attention was focused on non-synonymous mutations in individuals with DDD, removed the Indel and SNP appearing in each database, got the first-level database. Subsequently, took the intersection of the first -level database , which is the unique mutations of the two patients, here got the second-level database. And then filtered mutations affect "LOW" and "MEDIUM" mutation in the secondary database. NOW we got three-level database. Of the 57 variations, 19 variations were found to be disease-related , 38 were not found to be related to disease , and of the 19 mutation sites, only *PSENEN* was related to skin diseases. According to the previous literature, mutations in the *PSENEN* can cause clinical manifestations similar to DDD^[11-12]. And used Mutation Taster software predicts the c.168_169delTG of *PSENEN* , the result is " Disease". Therefore, considering that the c.168_169delTG of *PSENEN* may cause disease in the family. Additionally, there was no abnormalities identified in the *KRT5*, *POFUT1* and *POGLUT1*.

Sanger sequencing

We confirmed by sanger sequencing in seven patients (II:3, II:8, III:6, III:10, III:25, IV:12, IV:13). this mutation was present in seven affected family members. Furthermore, this mutation was absent in both seven unaffected family members(III :12, III:19, IV:7, IV:16, IV:17, IV:21, IV:22) and 100 unrelated healthy controls(Figure 4).

Fig 4. Sanger sequencing revealed a frameshift mutation c.168_169delTG of *PSENEN* gene in patients with DDD and healthy controls.

Discussion

Dowling-Degos disease (DDD) is an autosomal dominant genetic dermatosis with typical onset of disease occurring in adolescence, and manifesting as reticulate pigmentation of the flexures^[3,7]. The pigmentation gradually increases over time. The clinical manifestations of the DDD family we found are different from the previously reported^[10-13-14]. In addition to the typical progressively reticulate pigmentation of the flexures. There are also pitted scars on the perioral area and comedones on the nose, face, neck and chest.

DDD has been attributed to a number of different gene mutations. Betz *et al* first demonstrated loss of function mutations of the *KRT5* in a DDD family in 2006^[8]. Basmanav *et al*^[9] used whole-exome sequencing in 13 unrelated DDD individuals and identified *POGLUT1* as another DDD pathogenic gene. Additionally, in 2013, Li^[10] *et al* identified mutations of the *POFUT1* causing DDD. With the passage of time and the advancement of sequencing technology, we have found more and more DDD pathogenic genes, expressing that DDD has great genetic

heterogeneity. we performed whole-exome sequencing to detect the pathogenic gene responsible for this DDD family. After screening whole-exome sequencing results, we detected no mutations of *KRT5*, *POFUT1* and *POGLUT1*. However, we identified a novel frameshift mutation of the *PSENEN* gene in the DDD affected family. The *PSENEN* was previously thought to be a causative gene Inversa acne (AI)^[16]. The *PSENEN* gene is located on human chromosome 19q13.12 and encodes presenilin enhancer-2 (PEN-2), which is the final part of γ -secretase activity. PEN-2 is highly conserved and has 101 amino acids, which is essential for γ -secretase maturation and enzymatic activity^[17,18]. *PSENEN* gene mutation not only has close relationship with AI^[16], in recent years, we found that *PSENEN* gene mutation is also related to DDD and comanifestation of AI^[11]. DDD is a rare disease, that is less reported. Our findings add new evidence for the genetic heterogeneity of DDD

It has also been reported that *PSNENE* mutations cause the coexistence clinical manifestations of AI and DDD in some patients^[11-12]. Cheng Zhou *et al*^[11] investigated two Chinese families, pathogenic gene is *PSENEN*, with coexistence of AI and

DDD. The patients showed extensive asymptomatic comedones, pitted scars, multiple inflammatory papules, and nodules on the face, neck, and trunk, and reticulate pigmentation in the flexures areas. Damian J *et al* ^[12] also confirmed *PSENE*N as a pathogenic gene in six DDD patients. Half of patients presented with the chronic inflammatory skin disease AI, revealing that mutations in *PSENE*N can cause DDD and, in co-occurrence of trigger factors, also AI. However the family we found has typical clinical manifestations,reticulated pigmentation of the flexures, also presenting pitted scars and comedones on the face without deep painful nodules, abscesses, sinus tracts and scars. Our research subjects did not meet the diagnostic criteria of AI^[19].So we identified this is a DDD family , not a family of DDD merged with AI.

A frameshift mutation c.168_169delTG of *PSENE*N was identified mutation gene site of the family. This frameshift is different from the two mutations identified by Cheng Zhou et al which is a heterozygous missense mutation c.194T>G and a splice site mutation c.167-2A>G in the *PSENE*N ^[11].The 6 *PSENE*N mutations Damian J ^[12]*et al* reported comprised: 2 splice site mutations, c.62-1G>C and g.1412T>C); 2 nonsense mutations, c.35T>A and c.115C>T ;and 2 frameshift mutations, c.84_85insT and c.216delC This is the first time we have found this mutation site, which has not been reported before.

Conclusion

The lesions of this DDD individuals are different from those previously described, the patients present typical progressively reticulate pigmentation of the flexures and pitted scars and comedones on the face and flexion ,without clinical manifestations of AI. Our findings suggest that this novel frameshift mutation, c.168_169delTG, in *PSENE*N can be responsible for causing DDD in this family. This finding further enhances our understanding of the clinical features and genetic pathogenesis of DDD.

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Conflict of interest statement: All authors declare the absence of conflict for each author.

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